

THE EFFECT OF RADIAL STRESS RELAXATION ON FIBER STRESSES IN THICK FILAMENT-WOUND CYLINDERS

Evan A. Kempner and H. Thomas Hahn
University of California, Los Angeles
Los Angeles, CA 90024-1597

ABSTRACT

The stress redistribution due to fiber motion in thick, filament wound cylinders is analyzed in the present paper. An initial stress distribution in the wound cylinder is calculated based on an elastic analysis. The effect of subsequent fiber motion is described by a radial creep strain rate which is proportional to the radial stress. Numerical simulations have been performed for the stress redistribution in cylinders wound with winding tensions varying from 11.0 N to 44.5 N. The compressive axial fiber stress is shown to increase upon relaxation of compressive radial stress, the change increasing with the winding tension. Unfortunately, the new stress distributions favor fiber buckling.

Keywords: filament winding, fiber buckling, residual stresses, stress relaxation

1. INTRODUCTION

Filament winding is the predominant manufacturing process for composite cylinders. While winding of thin cylinders is fairly straightforward, fabrication of thick cylinders often results in wavy fiber tows which are detrimental to the compressive strength. Thus the stress development during the entire filament winding process must be known if optimum processing conditions are to be chosen for thick cylinders.

The main stages of the filament winding process during which fiber wrinkling may occur are the winding and curing. During winding, continuous bands of resin impregnated fibers are wrapped onto a rotating mandrel. In wet winding, fiber tows are pulled through a liquid resin bath for impregnation whereas fibers preimpregnated with B-staged resin are utilized in dry winding. For accurate placement of fiber tows on the mandrel and to improve compaction, a tensile force called the winding tension is applied to the fiber tows. The winding tension exerts radial pressure on the previously wound layers and compacts the cylinder. Compaction occurs primarily because fibers are not completely straight. The radial fiber motion associated with the compaction reduces the tension in the fibers. When the cylinder is thick, the axial fiber stress inside the cylinder can even be compressive, causing the fibers to buckle. However, the very radial pressure that causes compaction also supports the fibers and helps prevent buckling. Thus, the compressive axial fiber stress and the compressive radial stress are the two competing mechanisms for fiber buckling.

As the fiber tows are compacted, the resin is squeezed out. The rate of flow due to compaction will depend on the viscosity of the resin. In dry winding, resins of higher viscosity are used, and hence relatively little resin flow occurs during winding itself. However, during curing, the temperature rise causes a drop in the resin viscosity, and the resin can flow easily accompanied by fiber motion until cure sets in.

The stress development during winding has been studied by a number of investigators [1-5]. A comprehensive discussion on the stress development at various stages of filament winding process is given by Tarnapol'skii and Beil' [1]. One of the difficulties with the stress analysis is that the effective stress-strain behavior in the radial direction is nonlinear. Tarnapol'skii and Beil' [1] presented results based on linear, piecewise linear and nonlinear elastic analyses. Cai et al. [4] used a piecewise linear elastic analysis while Lee, Springer, et al. [2, 3] as well as Spencer [5] used a linear elastic analysis based on an effective radial modulus. Since these investigators except [1] were interested in modeling the whole filament winding process, no experimental correlation was provided for the stresses due to winding only.

Recently, Hahn and Lee [6] investigated the stress development during winding of dry glass fibers on a circular mandrel of 58-mm diameter. The wound composite cylinders were about 25 mm thick containing more than 100 layers. They used a linear elastic analysis and found an effective radial modulus by fitting the prediction to the experimentally measured pressure at the mandrel surface. The ratio of the hoop modulus to the inferred radial modulus was in the order of 10^4 , indicating a much higher anisotropy than discussed by Tarnapol'skii and Beil' [1]. From the theory-experiment correlation they concluded that the axial fiber stress was compressive, although small in magnitude, throughout most of the cylinder thickness [6]. The compressive nature of the fiber stress was also pointed out in [1].

While the small elastic compressive stresses resulting from winding are unlikely to cause fiber buckling, any fiber motion through the viscous resin may change the state of stress further to favor fiber buckling. The change of stress resulting from fiber motion has been studied by the same investigators mentioned earlier [2-5]. In all cases, the Darcy's law was used in one form or another to represent the resin flow.

The present paper describes an analysis to determine the effect of fiber motion on the stress redistribution in a filament-wound cylinder. Unlike the previous approaches, the radial strain due to fiber motion is represented by a radial creep strain. Thus the present approach is more appropriate when the fiber motion is the result of the slack in the wound cylinder rather than of the fibers moving through a liquid resin. The main objective is to determine whether or not the radial creep will lead to increased compression of fibers in thick cylinders. Because winding tension is the main parameter controlled during filament winding, simulations are performed to understand how winding tension will affect the stress development during winding and curing.

2. ANALYSIS

Consider a filament-wound cylinder which has just been wound. During winding, stress relaxation is assumed to be negligible. As the cylinder waits for curing, however, fibers start to move radially. The fiber movement can also be during curing. In any case, the severity of fiber movement will depend on the resin viscosity and the amount of slack in the wound cylinder. The objective here is to find the stress redistribution resulting from such fiber movement.

A linear elastic winding analysis is described in detail in [6]. The stresses due to winding are obtained from a plane-stress solution for a cylindrically orthotropic ring. The stress field and fiber positions calculated from the winding analysis are the initial conditions for the stress relaxation analysis resulting from fiber motion.

The initial radial and hoop stresses induced by winding are denoted σ_r^o and σ_θ^o , respectively. The total stresses in the cylinder are then given by

$$\sigma_r^T = \sigma_r^o + \sigma_r \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_\theta^T = \sigma_\theta^o + \sigma_\theta \quad (2)$$

where σ_r and σ_θ are the additional stresses resulting from fiber movement. When there is a slack and the resin viscosity is low, fibers will move into positions to reduce the radial stress as much as possible. The resulting radial strain is a creep strain and is denoted by ε_r^c . Furthermore, the creep strain rate is assumed to be proportional to the total radial stress:

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_r^c}{\partial t} = K \sigma_r^T \quad (3)$$

In the present analysis, K is assumed to be a constant. However, in reality, it would depend on the fiber volume fraction.

The stresses induced by the radial creep satisfy the equilibrium equation

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} = 0 \quad (4)$$

The stress-strain relations are given by

$$\varepsilon_r - \varepsilon_r^c = \frac{\sigma_r}{E_r} - \nu_{r\theta} \frac{\sigma_\theta}{E_\theta} \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_\theta = \frac{\sigma_\theta}{E_\theta} - \nu_{\theta r} \frac{\sigma_r}{E_r} \quad (6)$$

and the strain-displacement relations by

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \quad (7)$$

$$\varepsilon_\theta = \frac{u}{r} \quad (8)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3)-(8) into Eq. (4) results in the following equation for u :

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{E_\theta}{E_r} u = \frac{\partial \varepsilon_r^c}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \varepsilon_r^c \left(\nu_{\theta r} \frac{E_\theta}{E_r} + 1 \right) \quad (9)$$

The other equation required for ε_r^c is found by substituting Eqs. (2), (5) and (6) into Eq. (3):

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_r^c}{\partial t} + \frac{KE_r}{1 - \nu_{\theta r} \nu_{r\theta}} \varepsilon_r^c = K \left(\sigma_r^o + \frac{E_r}{1 - \nu_{\theta r} \nu_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \nu_{r\theta} \frac{u}{r} \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

The mandrel is assumed to be much stiffer than the composite cylinder, so that the radial displacement of the composite cylinder vanishes at its inner boundary. The radial stress at the outer boundary is zero as no external pressure is applied. With these boundary conditions, the above equations can be solved. Since the initial stresses, σ_r^o and σ_θ^o , are known at discrete points within the wound cylinder, the partial differential equations will be solved numerically.

Numerical solution of the partial differential equations is obtained by iterating between an explicit finite difference equation for creep strain and an implicit finite difference equation for the radial displacement [7]. The explicit finite difference form of Eq. (10) is given by

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{j+1,k}^c - \varepsilon_{j,k}^c}{\Delta t} + KA \varepsilon_{j,k}^c = K \sigma_r^o + KA \left(\frac{u_{j+1,k+1} - u_{j+1,k}}{\Delta r} + \frac{\nu_{r\theta}}{r_k} u_{j,k} \right) \quad (11)$$

where $A = \frac{E_r}{1 - \nu_{\theta r} \nu_{r\theta}}$, and j and k denote the previous time and radius steps, respectively. On the other hand, Eq. (9) is changed into an implicit finite difference equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{u_{j+1,k+1} - 2u_{j+1,k} + u_{j+1,k-1}}{(\Delta r)^2} + \frac{1}{r_k} \frac{u_{j+1,k+1} - u_{j+1,k-1}}{2\Delta r} - \frac{B}{r_k^2} u_{j+1,k} \\ & = \frac{\varepsilon_{j+1,k+1}^c - \varepsilon_{j+1,k-1}^c}{2\Delta r} - \frac{1}{r_k} C \varepsilon_{j+1,k-1}^c \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $B = \frac{E_r}{E_r}$ and $C = \nu_{\theta r} B + 1$.

Since $u_{j+1,k}$ is not known *a priori*, $u_{j+1,k}$ is taken to be equal to $u_{j,k}$ for the first iteration. Applying the initial conditions, $u_{0,k} = \varepsilon_{0,k}^c = 0$, $\varepsilon_{1,k}^c$ can be solved at all k increments. With $\varepsilon_{j+1,k}$ known from Eq.

(11) and applying the boundary conditions, $u_{j,0} = 0$ and $\frac{u_{j,n} - u_{j-1,n}}{\Delta r} = 0$ where n is the total number of layers, $u_{j+1,k}$ can be determined for all k by solving the k simultaneous equations in Eq. (12). The new value for $u_{j+1,k}$ is then used in Eq. (11) to recalculate $\varepsilon_{j+1,k}$. The iterative process continues until there is no appreciable difference between iterations.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A computer program was written to calculate stresses and strains resulting from stress relaxation after winding using the finite difference formulation described in the preceding section. The initial stress state in the cylinder was calculated using the linear elastic winding analysis detailed in [6].

Simulations were performed to calculate the stress development during winding and the subsequent stress relaxation for winding tensions varying between 11.0 N and 44.5 N. The input properties used are listed in Table 1. These properties were inferred from the results of Reference [6].

The creep constant, K , was estimated using data from consolidation experiments included in [4]. Pressure sensors located on the mandrel surface were used to measure the variation in mandrel pressure during consolidation of a cylindrical part. Test results showed a large pressure decrease with time which gradually approached a constant value after about 60 minutes. The length of time required for relaxation of the mandrel pressure was considered in choosing a value for K . A value of $6.9 \times 10^{-9} \text{ (MPa} \cdot \text{sec)}^{-1}$ was found to cause a similar response as that shown in [4].

The predicted mandrel pressure as a function of time is shown in Fig. 1 for four winding tensions. While the initial pressures due to winding range from 0.3 MPa to 1.4 MPa, they decrease exponentially with time and all converge close to 0.1 MPa after about 60 minutes of relaxation. Therefore, regardless of winding tension, the time required for complete stress relaxation is approximately the same. Also, because mandrel pressure can be conveniently measured by placing pressure sensors at the mandrel-composite interface, experimental determination of the creep constant can be obtained by correlation with the predicted mandrel pressure for a specific cylinder.

Figure 2 shows the initial and final radial stress distributions for a cylinders wound with 11.0 N and 44.5 N winding tensions. While, initially, the radial stresses are much higher for the higher winding tension, after relaxation, radial stresses drop below 0.05 MPa throughout both cylinders. Therefore, fiber support due to the radial stresses will be no greater for cylinders wound with large winding tensions. This is an important result because compressive circumferential stresses after winding were found to be larger for cylinders wound with high winding tensions.

The circumferential stress distribution at several times during relaxation is shown in Fig. 3. Initially, the circumferential stress is slightly compressive through most of the cylinder. As stress relaxation occurs, the magnitude of circumferential stress increases with the greatest increase occurring at the outer layer. Figure 4 shows the change in the maximum compressive stress versus time for each winding tension. A large increase in the circumferential compressive stresses is seen to occur due to stress relaxation. For the lowest winding tension, 11.0 N, the maximum compressive stress increases by a factor of 5.7, while for the highest winding tension, 44.5 N, the maximum compressive stresses increases by a factor of 5.1. Therefore, while compressive stresses are generally larger in cylinders wound with higher tension, the increase due to stress stress relaxation is slightly greater in cylinders wound with lower tension. Changes in the fiber volume fraction resulting from the stress relaxation are shown in Fig. 5. Aside from the region near the outer boundary, the fiber volume fraction changes very little.

The predicted change in the state of stress due to fiber movement favors fiber buckling. The compressive axial fiber stress increases while the compressive radial stress decreases. Since the latter prevents fibers from buckling, the probability of fiber buckling increases during stress relaxation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, a model was developed to predict the stress redistribution caused by stress relaxation after winding. The relaxation may occur during the waiting period before curing or during curing itself. The stress relaxation was effectively accounted for by using a creep constant in the radial direction. Simulations were performed for thick cylinders wound with glass fibers. Winding tension was varied from 11.0 N to 44.5 N.

Although the axial compression on fibers was rather small right after winding, it can increase substantially during stress relaxation. In fact, simulations indicate that the axial compression can increase by as much as a factor of five. Furthermore, the compressive radial stress, which provides lateral support for the fibers, decreases in magnitude. Also, while the initial radial stresses were highest for the winding tension of 44.5 N, the final radial stress distribution decreased to about 0.5 MPa for all winding tensions. The net result is a heightened probability of fiber buckling during stress relaxation.

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Table 1. Input properties

Property	Composite			
	Winding Tension, N			
	11.00	22.25	33.50	44.50
E_{θ} , GPa	36.24	36.24	36.24	36.24
$\nu_{\theta r}$	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22
E_r , MPa	4.31	5.17	6.03	6.89
V_f	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Layer Thickness, μm	224	224	224	224
Number of Layers	100	100	100	100

Mandrel

$E_m = 68.95 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m = 0.33$, inner radius = 25.4 mm, outer radius = 28.8 mm

Figure 1. Change in mandrel pressure with time

Figure 2. Initial and final radial stress distributions, $T = 11.0 \text{ N}$ and $T = 44.5 \text{ N}$

Figure 3. Initial and final circumferential stress distributions, $T = 44.5 \text{ N}$

Figure 4. Change in maximum compressive stress with time

Figure 5. Distribution of fiber volume fraction after 60 minutes of stress relaxation